

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

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Regulatory watch 2022-2023

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Summary

This report compiles all the issues of ZeroPM's monthly Regulatory watch for the end of 2022 and the full year 2023.

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1 Regulatory Watch September / October 2022

Publication of Commission Work Programme 2023

The [Commission Work Programme 2023](#) was published on 18 October. It confirms that the REACH revision is delayed until the end of 2023. The list of initiative included in the work programme does not include the revision of the Food contact material legislation, for which the public consultation is currently open. Similarly, expected legislative proposals for the announced revisions of the Cosmetics Regulation and the Toys Directive are not on the list. The full list of initiatives can be found in the Annexes to the work programme.

ENVI Committee asks Commission not to delay REACH Revision

A number of MEPs from the ENVI Committee have written a [letter](#) to the Commission asking to not delay the revisions of REACH and CLP and to publish the two proposals at the latest by early 2023. This letter responds to the [EPP Group asking the Commission](#) for a 'regulatory moratorium' to delay acts that would 'unnecessarily increase costs for businesses (such as REACH)'.

Upcoming deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft delegated act](#) introducing new hazard classes and criteria in CLP Regulation: 18 October 2022
- ▼ Deadline to participate in the [public consultation](#) on the upcoming Soil Health Law: 24 October 2022
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [SVHC dossier](#) for melamine: 17 October 2022
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [SVHC dossier](#) for Perfluoroheptanoic acid and its salts: 17 October 2022

New consultation processes:

- ▼ Launch of the [public consultation](#) on the revision of the Food Contact Material legislation – deadline to respond on 11 January 2023.

2 Regulatory Watch November 2022

Publication of the Zero Pollution Package:

On 26 October, the Commission published the [Commission proposals](#) for revising the lists of surface and groundwater pollutants (WFD, EQS and Groundwater Directives), revising the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive, and the Ambient Air Quality Directive. Main changes are highlighted below.

Proposal for the revision of the revision of the WFD, EQSD and GWD:

Amendments to Groundwater Directive:

- ▼ New Article 6a makes the ‘Watch List Mechanism’ for groundwater bodies **mandatory** and establishes a three year review process for the watch list feeding into a six yearly revision of quality standards (Annex I). Also includes an obligation for ECHA to make the scientific reports prepared in relation to the Watch List publicly available.
- ▼ New Article 8: provisions on the revision of the Annexes by means of the legislative procedure are deleted and replaced by provisions granting powers to the Commission for amending the Annexes through **delegated acts** – e.g. for listing new groundwater pollutants in Annex I and establishing new EU-wide quality standards. This should facilitate and accelerate the adoption of amendments to the annexes.
- ▼ Annex I on EU wide quality standards for groundwater pollutants is amended to insert new groundwater pollutants and related **quality standard for some PFAS**, pharmaceuticals and non-relevant metabolites of pesticides. Regarding PFAS, a quality standard is introduced for the **sum of 24 PFAS: 0,0044 µg/l**. List of substances is in attached Annexes (Annex III). The standard is in line with the opinion of the SCHEER of August 2022.

Amendments to EQSD:

- ▼ Article 8 : provisions granting powers to the Commission to revise Annex I every six years through **delegated acts** (instead of legislative procedure) in order to consider listing new priority substances and related EQS, based on input by ECHA. Also contains an obligation for ECHA to make scientific reports related to the amendment of the Annexes publicly available.
- ▼ Article 8b: sets a three year review cycle for the surface water Watch List instead of the current two year cycle to give more time to process the data before revising the list and extends the monitoring cycle from 12 to 24 months to allow better consideration of different frequencies for pollutants with seasonal emission patterns (e.g. pesticides/biocides)
- ▼ Annex I: 23 new substances are added to the list of priority substances including pharmaceuticals, industrial substances, pesticides and metals. The Annex also indicates the substances that are hazardous, those that are ubiquitous PBTs as well as those that require long-term trend assessment. Among the 23 new substances, **an EQS is defined for the sum of the concentrations of the 24 PFAS expressed as PFOA-equivalents : 0,0044 µg/l (surface water) and**

0,077 µg/kg wet weigh (biota). List of substances is in attached Annexes (Annex V). The EQS is in line with the opinion of the SCHEER of August 2022.

Proposal for the revision of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive:

- ▼ New article 8 on Quaternary treatment: obligation to apply additional treatment to urban wastewater in order to eliminate the broadest possible spectrum of micro-pollutants.
- ▼ New Article 9 on Extended producer responsibility: obligation for producers (including importers) of certain products (pharmaceuticals and personal care products only) to contribute to the costs of the quaternary treatment.
- ▼ Revision of Article 15 on water reuse: Paragraph 1 has been amended so that Member States will be required to systematically promote the reuse of treated wastewater from all urban wastewater treatment plants.
- ▼ New Article 17 Urban wastewater surveillance : establishes a national urban wastewater monitoring system to monitor relevant public health parameters in urban wastewater.
- ▼ New Article 18 on Risk assessment and management: obligation for Member States to assess the risks caused by urban wastewater discharges to the environment and human health, and, where necessary, take additional measures on top of this Directive's minimum requirements to address these risks.
- ▼ Revision of Article 20 on sludge: sludge will have to be treated, recycled and recovered whenever appropriate and disposed of in accordance with the requirements of the Waste Framework Directive and the Sludge Directive.
- ▼ Revision of article 21 on monitoring: For all agglomerations of above 10 000 population equivalent, Member States must monitor at the inlets and outlets of urban wastewater treatment plants, the concentration and loads in the urban wastewater of pollutants listed in EQSD, Groundwater Directive, E-PRTR, Sewage sludge Directive and the presence of microplastics including in the sludge.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the lists of surface and groundwater pollutants: **23 December 2022**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive: **23 December 2022**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Ambient Air Quality Directive: **23 December 2022**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the revision of the Food Contact Material legislation: **11 January 2023**.

Other EU policy updates:

- ▼ Council adopted on 24 October the [revision](#) of the POPs Regulation adding new substances – including PFOA, its salts and PFOA-related compounds, PFHxS,

its salts and PFHxS-related compounds – to Annex IV setting concentration limits of POPs in waste.

- ▼ Several Member States voiced support for the REACH revision in the Environment Council – 24.10.22: Austria, Denmark, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands and Sweden regretted the postponement of the Commission proposal and called for its publication as soon as possible. Commissioner responded that the proposal will be presented as soon as finalised – before the end of 2023 if ready.
- ▼ Belgium put the subject of PFAS on the agenda of the Environment Council on 24.10.22 and provided an [information note](#) to the Council. In addition to supporting a broad PFAS restriction and addressing PFAS in each relevant piece of legislation, Belgium supports increased exchange of information and cooperation between Member States on decontamination practices and techniques.
- ▼ General support from Member States to the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation and the digital product passport in Council. In ENVI council, five Member States stressed the necessity ensure alignment of the Regulation with REACH (IE, LV, LT, PL, SI) but no major issues were raised in relation to ecodesign requirements for substances of concern. Other concerns were raised in relation to costs for SMEs, practical implementation and enforcement of the Regulation and ease of use of the digital product passport for consumers.

3 Regulatory Watch December 2022

Revision of REACH and CLP Regulations

- ▼ The second Ad-hoc CARACAL on the CLP Delegated Act happened on 29 November 2022. The publication of the final delegated act is planned for 19 December. According to EEB and Chemtrust, the PMT/vPvM criteria improved, with the removal of a phrase requested by industry to make the identification of mobility more difficult. It seems the proposed criteria will be the final ones.
- ▼ The Commission's draft impact assessment for the revision of REACH received the green light from the Regulatory Scrutiny Board on 17 November 2022. The Regulatory Scrutiny Board is an independent body within the Commission issuing opinions and recommendations on all the Commission's draft impact assessments, fitness checks, and major evaluations of existing legislation. Its positive opinion is mandatory before an initiative with an impact assessment can be adopted by the Commission. The Commission can now start preparing the legislative proposal – which could be adopted earlier than Autumn 2023 as planned in the Commission Work Programme (possibly spring 2023).

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [call for evidence](#) on the Fitness check of the application of the polluter-pay principle: **9 December 2022**. A public consultation will follow in the first quarter of 2023.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the revision of the Food Contact Material legislation: **11 January 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the lists of surface and groundwater pollutants: **27 January 2023 (extended)**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive: **27 January 2023 (extended)**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Ambient Air Quality Directive: **27 January 2023 (extended)**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) for a Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste: **27 January 2023**.

Other EU policy updates:

- ▼ The Commission adopted on 30 November its Circular Economy Package including the [Commission proposal](#) for a Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste and a [Communication](#) on an EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics.
- ▼ The first Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Report will be presented at the [Zero Pollution Stakeholder Conference](#) on 14/12/2022. The implementation of the Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Framework stems from the Zero Pollution Action Plan and aims to monitor overall pollution levels and impacts in order to track progress towards achieving the objectives of the Green Deal.

A second Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Report will be published in 2024.

- ▼ The [Commission Recommendation](#) establishing a European assessment framework for 'safe and sustainable by design' chemicals and materials has just been published.

4 Regulatory watch January 2023

Adoption of new CLP hazard classes

The [Delegated Regulation](#) setting out new regards hazard classes and criteria, including for PMT / vPvM substances has been adopted on 19 December 2022. The Regulation will enter into force early this year (mid-February), after scrutiny by the European Parliament and Council.

CLP revision

Together with the adopted delegated act, the Commission published on 19 December 2022 a [proposal for the revision of the CLP Regulation](#). The proposed revision adds the new hazard classes to the hazards that are normally subject to harmonised classification and labelling (amendments to Article 36 of the CLP Regulation). The proposal introduces the possibility for the Commission to initiate the harmonised classification and labelling procedure by requesting ECHA or EFSA to prepare a CLH proposal for a substance (amendments to Article 37 of the CLP Regulation). This possibility was so far only provided to Member States competent authorities and manufacturers, importers and downstream users. The possibility to initiate harmonised classification and labelling proposals for several substances at once is also added to the Regulation. The [consultation](#) on the draft Commission proposal is open until 28 February 2023.

Melamine

The Member States Committee [identified Melamine as SVHC](#) in December 2022.

Regulation on maximum levels of PFAS in certain foodstuffs

The [Commission Regulation](#) amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards maximum levels of perfluoroalkyl substances in certain foodstuffs has been adopted on 7 December 2022. Addressing the presence of PFAS in food by introducing limits in the legislation on food contaminants was in the action plan of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 sets maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs listed in Annex to the Regulation. The amending Regulation sets maximum levels in food (eggs, fish, crustaceans and meat) for PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, and PFHxS. The limit values have been adopted based on EFSA's opinion of 9 July 2020 on the risk to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. The Regulation entered into force on 1 January 2023.

Zero pollution monitoring and outlook

The European Environmental Agency presented their first Zero pollution monitoring assessment and the Commission Joint Research Center the Zero pollution outlook 2022 at the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Conference on 14 December 2022. The presentations from the conference are available [here](#).

The Zero pollution monitoring assessment assesses progress towards the [six targets](#) set out for 2030 in the Zero Pollution Action Plan of 2021. The EEA concluded that the two targets to 'reduce the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50 %' and to 'reduce the use of the more hazardous chemical pesticides by 50 %'. EEA's report is available [here](#)

(most relevant chapters are the ‘[production](#)’ section and the [health chapter](#)) and the Commission’s Zero pollution monitoring and outlook report [here](#).

The JRC’s Zero pollution outlook 2022 presents modelling and foresight results which provide a broader perspective on whether the EU is on track with regard to the objectives of the EU zero pollution ambitions and associated EU legislation. The JRC’s report is available [here](#).

Swedish presidency of the Council

Sweden has taken up the presidency of the Council for the next six months, until end of June 2023. The Presidency’s [work programme](#) prioritises, in the Environment Council, the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive, the revision of the Ambient Air Quality Directives, and aims to advance the work on the revision of the Packaging Directive and on circular-economy related matters, in particular on ‘EU regulatory frameworks that promote non-toxic material cycles, increased use of high-quality recycled materials in products, and other business models that promote a circular economy’.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the revision of the Food Contact Material legislation: **11 January 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the lists of surface and groundwater pollutants: **28 February 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive: **28 February 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Ambient Air Quality Directive: **28 February 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) for a Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste: **28 February 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) amending the CLP Regulation: **28 February 2023**.

Upcoming regulatory milestones:

- ▼ **Transposition of the Drinking water Directive** (Directive (EU) 2020/2184) in all 27 Member States is due on **12 January 2023**.
- ▼ **PFAS Restriction:** The restriction proposal on the manufacture, placing on the market and use of PFAS, prepared by Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden, is expected to be submitted on **13 January 2023**.

5 Regulatory watch February 2023

PFAS restriction

The [proposal](#) to restrict PFAS under REACH, drafted by the national authorities of Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden, has been submitted to ECHA in January. The proposal was published on 7 February.

The restriction concerns all PFAS falling under the 2021 OECD definition, with the exception of ‘a few fully degradable PFAS subgroups’. The proposed restriction option provides for a ban on the manufacture, placing on the market and use of PFAS as substances on their own and bans the presence, in substances, mixtures or articles, of any non-polymeric PFAS above 25 parts per billion, while a limit for the sum of non-polymeric PFAS is set at 250 parts per billion. For polymeric PFAS, the limit would be set at 50 parts per million. An 18-month transition period is proposed before the entry into force of the restriction.

The restriction option excludes PFAS used as active substances in plant protection products, biocidal products, and human and veterinary medicinal products, which are covered by other regulations. It also provides for use-specific time-limited derogations (18-month transition period + 5- or 12-year derogation period depending on whether possible alternatives to the PFAS use have already been identified or not) for a wide range of products. 8 uses would benefit from a 5-year derogation and 16 from a 12-year derogation. A number of tentative derogations are included in the proposal and will be reconsidered after the public consultation.

The six-month public consultation will start on **22 March 2023** (until 22 September 2023). An online information session will be organised by ECHA on 5 April.

Candidate list

Following Member States Committee decisions in November and December, ECHA has added Melamine and Perfluoroheptanoic acid and its salts to the Candidate list on 17 January 2023.

Revision of food contact materials legislation delayed

The Commission has announced that the proposal for the revision of the food contact material legislation would not be published in the second quarter of 2023 as initially planned. According to a recent [Commission presentation](#), the impact assessment will be carried out in 2023-2024 and the work on the legislative proposal will take place in ‘2024 and beyond’, suggesting that the legislative procedure will be carried out under the next Commission. According to the same presentation, the generic approach to assessing chemical risk, based on hazard classifications, will be part of the proposal, although it does not specifically mention PMT/vPvM.

Chemical industry transition pathway

The updated EU 2021 industrial strategy set the objective of developing actions plans for achieving the ‘green and digital transition’ for selected industries. These action plans or ‘pathways’ are developed jointly by the Commission, EU Member States and

stakeholders (industry, social partners, NGOs and academia). The [Transition pathway for the chemical industry](#) has been published in January 2023. It lists a series of actions to be taken by chemical companies, the EU and Member States, and a timeline for their implementation. Among environmental objectives, the transition pathway reiterates the objectives of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability to ‘establish safe and sustainable chemicals as an EU global benchmark’ and to ban ‘most harmful substances in consumer products unless they are essential for society’. The implementation of the transition pathway will start in the second quarter of 2023.

Swedish presidency support to REACH revision

During an [exchange of views](#) with the Environment Committee of the European Parliament, Romina Pourmokhtari, Minister for Climate and Environment of Sweden, gave an overview of the priorities of the Swedish presidency on climate and environment policy. She recalled the Presidency’s aim to adopt Council mandates on many files including the Industrial Emissions Directive, the Ecodesign for sustainable products Regulation, to continue the legislative work on water, urban wastewater treatment and air legislation and start the work on the packaging and packaging waste Directive. She also stressed that the revision of REACH was a priority for Sweden and that the Presidency is ready to start the negotiations as soon as there is a proposal from the Commission. She recalled the full support of the Council to an ambitious REACH Revision, which was expressed in the Council conclusions of March 2021.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the draft Delegated act amending Annex I to the POPs Regulation to include PFHxS, its salts and PFHxS-related compounds (following inclusion in Annex A to the Stockholm Convention): **9 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the lists of surface and groundwater pollutants: **14 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive: **14 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Ambient Air Quality Directive: **14 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) amending the CLP Regulation: **30 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) for a Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste: **04 April 2023**.

New consultation:

The Commission’s recent proposal on an Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), currently undergoing legislative procedure, should be completed with a work plan, prioritising product groups and measures for the establishment of ecodesign requirements. The Commission seeks views on the categories of new products and measures to address first.

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [call for evidence and respond to the public consultation](#) on new product priorities under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation: **25 April 2023**.

6 Regulatory watch March 2023

REACH restriction on C9-C14 PFCAs enters into force

[REACH restriction](#) on perfluorocarboxylic acids containing 9 to 14 carbon atoms in the chain (C9-C14 PFCAs), their salts and C9-C14 PFCA-related substances (Annex XVII, entry 68), adopted in August 2021 entered into force on 25 February 2023. A proposal for listing Long-chain PFCAs their salts and related compounds in Annexes to the Stockholm Convention is also under review.

Amendment to Annex I to POPs Regulation – PFOA

An [amendment](#) to Annex I to the POPs regulation adopted on 24 February 2023 restricts the unintentional trace contaminant (UTC) limit of PFOA in polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) micropowders to 0,025 milligrams per kilogram (compared to the previous limit of 1 mg/kg).

European Parliament's ENVI Committee adopted its position on the revision of the F-gas Regulation

The [ENVI Committee's position](#), adopted on 1 March, increases the ambitions of the Commission legislative proposal by accelerating HFC phase down and introducing the objective a complete HFC production and consumption phase out in the EU by 2050. The Committee report adds prohibitions on the use of F-gases for sectors where it is technologically and economically feasible to switch to F-gases free alternatives, such as refrigeration, air conditioning, heat pumps and electrical switchgear.

Revision of the Groundwater Directive and EQS Directive – Draft report from European Parliament's Rapporteur proposes quality standard for 'PFAS total'

The European Parliament's Rapporteur for the revision of the EQS and Groundwater Directives proposed in its [draft report](#) published on 20 February to set a two-year deadline for the Commission to establish technical guidelines regarding methods for monitoring all PFAS in ground and surface water in order to establish an EQS and a groundwater quality standard for 'PFAS Total' (in addition to the EQS and groundwater standard set for the sum of 24 PFAS).

The Rapporteur also proposed to reintroduce the deadline for Member States to phase out priority hazardous substances no later than 20 years after they are listed in the EQS Directive, remove the maximum numbers of new and emerging substances that can be contained in the EU watch lists for surface (10 substances) and groundwater (5 substances) at the same time, to introduce provisions to ensure faster deployment of effect-based monitoring methods to combined effects of priority substances, and to introduce an extended producer responsibility scheme for funding ground and surface water monitoring programmes. The draft report will be discussed at the end of March, with a Committee vote planned for the end of May.

European Parliament's ENVI Committee members express strong concerns on the timing of the revision of REACH

On 1 March the ENVI Committee of the European Parliament organised an [exchange of views](#) with the Commission (DG Environment and DG GROW) on the upcoming

Commission proposal for the revision of REACH. Members of the ENVI Committee expressed strong concerns about the timing of the publication of the legislative proposal as a publication in Q4 of 2023, as announced by the Commission, is likely to delay the legislative process to after the European elections in 2024. Several Committee members called for an earlier publication of the Commission proposal in June 2023 to increase health and environment protection and give the industry more legal clarity for their investment decisions. The Commission reiterated the commitment to publish the proposal within the set timeline (Q4 2023) and, if possible, before, without taking further commitment on an earlier publication. The Commission confirmed that the generic approach to risk management, the essential use concept, the inclusion of polymers, combination effects and the introduction of a mixture assessment factor, and provisions to improve implementation and enforcement of the Regulation would be part of the legislative proposal.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Delegated act](#) amending Annex I to the POPs Regulation to include PFHxS, its salts and PFHxS-related compounds (following inclusion in Annex A to the Stockholm Convention): **9 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the lists of surface and groundwater pollutants: **14 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive: **14 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) revising the Ambient Air Quality Directive: **14 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) for a Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste: **24 April 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) amending the CLP Regulation: **30 March 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [call for evidence and respond to the public consultation](#) on new product priorities under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation: **12 May 2023**

Upcoming consultations

The public consultation on the PFAS restriction will start on **22 March 2023** and will be open until **22 September 2023**. An online information session on the consultation will be organised by ECHA on 5 April.

7 Regulatory watch April 2023

Opening of the public consultation on the PFAS restriction

The [public consultation](#) on the PFAS restriction is open until **22 September 2023**. An [online information session](#) on the consultation will be organised by ECHA on 5 April.

RAC and SEAC support the restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams

ECHA's Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC) and Committee for Socio-Economic Analysis (SEAC) have adopted their opinions and support the proposed restriction on the placing on the market, formulation and use of firefighting foams containing PFAS. The opinion of the SEAC is open for [consultation](#) for 60 days until 15 May 2023.

CoRAP update includes suspected vPvM

The [Community rolling action plan](#) (CoRAP) 2023-2025 contains 24 substances suspected of posing a risk to human health or the environment to be evaluated by Member State Competent Authorities under the substance evaluation process of the REACH Regulation. The update from March 2023 added six substances to the list included a suspected vPvM, Sodium 3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-sec-butyl-4-hydroxybenzenesulfonate (CAS no. 92484-48-5), to be evaluated in 2023.

Delegated Regulation on new CLP hazard classes and criteria published in the Official Journal

The [Commission Delegated Regulation \(EU\) 2023/707](#) amending Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 as regards hazard classes and criteria for the classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, introducing the new hazard class for PMT and vPvM substances has been published in the Official Journal of the European Union on 31 March 2023. The Regulation will officially enter into force on the twentieth day following its publication in the Official Journal, on 20 April 2023. Transitional periods for the classification and labelling of PMT/vPvM substances however apply: PMT/vPvM substances should be classified and labelled according to the criteria of the Regulation by 1 May 2025 (1 November 2026 for substances placed on the market before 1 May 2025) and mixtures by 1 May 2026 (1 May 2028 for mixtures placed on the market before 1 May 2026).

Adoption of the Implementing Regulation on the identification of unacceptable co-formulants in plant protection products

The [implementing Regulation](#) setting out detailed rules for the identification of unacceptable co-formulants in plant protection products was adopted on 13 March 2023 (it was published in the OJ on 14 March and is now in force). The Regulation sets criteria to determine whether a co-formulant might have harmful effect on human or animal health or on groundwater or unacceptable effects on the environment as per Article 27(1) of the Plant Protection Product Regulation (Regulation (EC) 1107/2009) and should consequently not be accepted for inclusion in a plant protection product. Those criteria include, among others, the classification of the co-formulant as CMR, its inclusion in the annexes to the POPs Regulation, its inclusion on the Candidate List (for reasons other than its classification as CMR) or as having endocrine-disrupting properties in accordance with the BPR. The criteria do not refer to new hazard classes under the CLP Regulation (e.g. PMT/vPvM). The Regulation also lays down rules for including new

substances in the list of co-formulant not accepted for inclusion in plant protection products (Annex III to the PPPR).

Draft report from European Parliament's Rapporteur on UWWTD calls for public funding to complement the EPR

The Commission proposal for the recast Directive on urban wastewater treatment, published in October 2022, proposed to introduce Extended producer responsibility (EPR) for producers of pharmaceuticals and cosmetic products to finance the costs of quaternary treatment, newly introduced in the Directive, to remove micro-pollutants from waste water. The [draft report](#) from European Parliament's Rapporteur proposes to share the responsibility of financing quaternary treatment between the EPR, governments and the public, though the establishment of 'national financing programmes'. These programmes would be financed through contributions from national funding, municipal levies, existing water tariffs, and by those producers. The rapporteur also calls on the Commission to assess by 2030 the possible extension of the scope of the EPR to products containing PFAS placed on the market, taking into account any future restrictions. The draft report will be presented by the rapporteur to the European Parliament's ENVI Committee at the end of April.

Council reaches an agreement on the revision of the IED

The Council adopted its [general approach](#) on the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive on 16 March 2023. The Council proposed to add to the permit conditions (Article 14 of the IED) and the Environmental Management System (EMS) (Article 14a) a focus on the prevention and reduction of the emissions of the most hazardous substances, including 'substances fulfilling the criteria of article 57 or substances addressed in restrictions in Annex XVII to the REACH Regulation'. The Council agreement also introduces transitional periods for competent Authorities and installations to comply with the new provisions of 16 years for existing activities and 10 years for new activities. Further details on changes made by the Council can be found in the [excel sheet](#). The adoption of the Parliament's position is expected in June and the trialogues in September.

European Parliament's amendments and Council draft mandate for the revision of the F-gas Regulation adopted in Plenary

The European Parliament adopted on 30 March 2023 its [amendments](#) to the Commission proposal on the recast F-gas Regulation. MEPs largely backed the report from the ENVI Committee calling for complete HFC production and consumption phase out in the EU by 2050. The EP amendments make a clear link between F-gases and PFAS pollution. The amendments state that the 'Regulation should not encourage substitution of HFCs with fluorinated greenhouse gases that are also PFAS, whose production produces PFAS or otherwise decomposes into PFAS' and introduce an obligation for the Commission to assess, within three months following the adoption of the revised REACH Regulation, the coherence between the revised F-gas Regulation and the revised REACH Regulation, and if necessary to publish a legislative proposal to align the F-gas Regulation with REACH. The [compromise text](#) from the Council from 31 March 2023 is not as ambitious as the Parliament's position and does not include a complete phase out by 2050. It generally maintains the phase down schedule of the Commission

proposal, except for first two periods where the maximum ceiling is increased (42.87 million tonnes of CO2 equivalent in 2024-26 and 20.68 MT CO2e in 2027-29). It also postpones the ban dates for some equipment and delays the ban the use of newly produced SF6 in servicing to 2035. Contrary to the Parliament's amendments, the compromise text does not address HFCs' substitution by F-gases that are PFAS, produce and/or degrade into PFAS. The compromise text still has to be formally endorsed by the Council. Further details can be found in the [excel sheet](#).

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [draft Commission Proposal](#) for a Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste: **24 April 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [call for evidence and respond to the public consultation](#) on new product priorities under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation: **12 May 2023**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft opinion of the SEAC on the restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams: **15 May 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the PFAS restriction: **25 September 2023**

Transposition of the Drinking water Directive (updates)

- ▼ Flanders has adopted a limit value for the Sum of 4 PFAS (PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFOS) of 4 ng/L. Operators must comply with the limit value within five years after the adoption of the Decree, i.e. March 2028.
- ▼ Italy has adopted a parameter 'Sum of PFAS' covering 24 substances: the 20 PFAS listed in the Drinking Water Directive and: 2,3,3,3-tetrafluoro-2-(heptafluoropropoxy)propanoic acid (HFPO-DA or GenX); dodecafluoro-3H-4,8-dioxanonanoic acid (ADONA); fluorotelomer sulphonate (6:2 FTS); Acetic acid / 2,2-difluoro-2-((2,2,4,5-tetrafluoro-5-(trifluoromethoxy)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)oxy)- (C6O4).

8 Regulatory watch May 2023

New CLP hazard classes have entered into force, ECHA updates relevant guidance and tools

The new CLP hazard classes entered into force on 20 April 2023. New requirements will apply to new substances from 1 May 2025 (and from 1 November 2026 for substances placed on the market before 1 May 2025). For new mixtures placed on the market, requirement will apply from 1 May 2026 (1 May 2028 for mixtures placed on the market before 1 May 2026). ECHA is currently [updating all guidance and tools](#) to include the new hazard classes: the harmonised classification and labelling (CLH) proposal template is already updated; new hazard classes will be included in the IT tool IUCLID in spring 2024 so that companies can submit information related to the new hazard classes; and the guidance on applying the CLP criteria is expected to be updated by mid-2024.

Commission proposal revising the pharmaceutical legislation strengthens provisions on environmental risk assessment of medicinal products

The Commission published on 26 April 2023 a [proposal for a new Directive and a new Regulation revising the general pharmaceutical legislation](#). The proposal strengthens the environmental risk assessment (ERA) of pharmaceuticals and requires that the ERA indicates whether the pharmaceutical product contains PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, or endocrine active agents. The ERA must also include risk mitigation measures to avoid or limit emissions to air, water and soil of pollutants listed in the Water Framework Directive, the Groundwater Directive, the Environmental Quality Standard Directive and the Industrial Emissions Directive. Under the new legal framework, the fact that the ERA does not provide enough evidence that environmental risks have been adequately evaluated and addressed through risk management measures becomes a ground for refusing the market authorisation, which was not the case in the previous legislation. The consultation on the Commission proposal is open until the end of June. More details on the proposed revision can be found in the excel sheet.

Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands and Czech Republic call for lowering maximum levels of PFAS in food and establishing maximum levels for additional foodstuffs

In December 2022, the European Commission introduced maximum levels for certain PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, and PFHxS) in certain foodstuffs of animal origin (eggs, meat, fish, fishery product and mussels). These maximum levels were based on EFSA's opinion of 9 July 2020 on the risk to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. Delegations from Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands and Czech Republic submitted a [note](#) that was [debated at the Agriculture and Fisheries Council](#) on 25 April 2023, recommending to regularly review and lower existing maximum levels for PFAS in foodstuffs, and to set new maximum levels in additional foodstuffs based on occurrence data in food. To achieve this, the note encourages all Member States to submit monitoring data to EFSA as requested by [Commission Recommendation \(EU\) 2022/1431](#). The Recommendation requests that Member States to monitor annually until 2025 levels of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and other PFAS in wide variety of foodstuffs including fruits, vegetables, cereals, oilseeds, or food for infants and young children. The European Commission stated that

maximum level should be considered for these products, in combination with measures to reduce sources of contamination. Some Member States however highlighted the current lack of data and analysis method to revise the maximum levels or add new ones.

ECHA launches call for evidence on 1,4-dioxane

On 20 April, ECHA launched a [call for evidence](#) to support Germany's upcoming restriction proposal on the manufacture, use and placing on the market of 1,4-dioxane containing surfactants. The restriction is based on the risk posed by this persistent and mobile substance to drinking water sources. The call for evidence, open until 20 June, aims to gather information on the manufacture, uses, emissions related to manufacture and uses, the feasibility of removal of 1,4-dioxane from other substances / mixtures the socio-economic impacts of a REACH restriction.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to comment on the [call for evidence and respond to the public consultation](#) on new product priorities under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation: **12 May 2023**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft opinion of the SEAC on the restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams: **15 May 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [comment on the proposal](#) for listing Long-chain perfluorocarboxylic acids, their salts and related compounds in Annexes to the Stockholm Convention – consultation on the draft Risk Management Evaluation: **17 May 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide input to the [call for evidence](#) on 1,4-dioxane as well as substances and mixtures containing 1,4-dioxane as a constituent or an impurity (aiming to support the preparation of a Restriction Report): **20 June 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the Commission proposal for the revision of the EU general pharmaceuticals legislation: **28 June 2023** (to be extended).
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the PFAS restriction: **25 September 2023**.

9 Regulatory watch June 2023

Council general approach on the Ecodesign for Sustainable Product Regulation further clarifies interface with REACH

The Council maintained the broad definition of 'substance of concern' as in the Commission proposal, which includes PMT/vPvM substances. The [general approach](#) however further clarifies that ecodesign and performance requirements adopted under the ESPR should not restrict the use of substances in products based on chemical safety or food safety reasons but for reasons relating primarily to circularity and sustainability of the product (e.g. substances that hinders the reuse or recycling of products). This clarification aims to better define the interface between the ESPR and other legislative frameworks, in particular with REACH. Relevant substances that 'negatively affects the re-use and recycling of materials in the product' should be determined as part of the prior assessment before setting ecodesign criteria for a product group. The Council also provides a minimum transition period of 18 months before the entry into force of ecodesign requirements.

Council general approach slightly extends the list of pollutants for which reporting requirements can be set

The Council [general approach](#) on the Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation, adopted on 8 June 2023, slightly broadens the scope pollutants that may be added to Annex II (i.e. the pollutants that need to be reported above set thresholds) adding to the list substances restricted under REACH (only SVHCs were listed in the Commission proposal) and substances listed in the watch list of the Drinking water Directive. Although the Council partly limits the empowerment of the Commission to adopt delegated acts, it is maintained for adding pollutants in Annex II and setting and updating thresholds for releases. The Council postpones the application of the Regulation by two years (to 2028 instead of 2026), to leave time to Member States adapt to the new rules.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ deadline to contribute to the [call for evidence](#) on 1,4-dioxane as well as substances and mixtures containing 1,4-dioxane as a constituent or an impurity: **20 June 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to contribute to the [call for evidence](#) and the [open public consultation](#) on the impact assessment to ensure that hazardous chemicals banned or severely restricted in the EU are not produced for export: **31 July 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to reply to the open public consultation for the fitness check of the application of the polluter-pay principle: **4 August 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation: **6 August 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the PFAS restriction: **25 September 2023**

10 Regulatory watch July 2023

SEAC final opinion supports proposed restriction on PFAS in firefighting foams

[SEAC adopted in June its final opinion supporting a gradual ban on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances \(PFAS\) in firefighting foams](#). SEAC considered the proposed restriction as the ‘most appropriate EU-wide measure to address the identified risks’. The Committee recommended reviewing at the end of the transitional period available alternatives for uses at industrial sites that produce, treat or store dangerous substances, covered by the Seveso Directive, and offshore oil and gas platforms. It also recommended longer transitional periods (10 years instead of five) for offshore oil and gas installations and shipping. ECHA will prepare the combined opinion of both committees and send it to the Commission, which will decide whether to draft a restriction proposal under Annex XVII of the REACH Regulation.

Proposal for Soil Monitoring Law requires identification and remediation of contaminated sites

On 5 July, the European Commission adopted a [proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience](#), which addresses soil contamination. The proposed Directive requires Member States to identify potentially contaminated sites within seven years of the entry into force of the Directive, investigate those sites to confirm the presence of contamination, and to set up a register of contaminated sites and potentially contaminated sites within four years. The Directive also requires Member States to carry out site-specific risk assessment to determine whether the contaminated sites pose unacceptable risks to human health or the environment and, in such cases, to take appropriate risk reduction and remediation measures. The determination of what constitutes an unacceptable risk for human health and the environment is however left to each Member State. The timeframe and prioritisation of soil investigations is also left to Member States and no timeframe for remediation (other than the general objective of achieving healthy soils by 2050) is set by the Directive. The Commission proposal will soon be put to consultation on [Have your Say](#).

Council adopts its position on the revision of the CLP Regulation

The Council adopted its [position](#) on the revision of the CLP Regulation on 30 June 2023. The position clarified certain labelling requirements including for online sale and clarified rules for digital labelling. Echoing concerns already expressed by the Parliament, it removed provisions on chemical substances with more than one constituent (MOCS) and requests the Commission to present a report on applicable rules for the classification of these substances four years after the date of entry into force of the revised CLP Regulation. Regarding the new hazard classes, the Council amended the provisions to avoid duplication of assessments carried out under different legislation (REACH, PPPR, BPR).

European Parliament’s ENVI Committee adds PMT/vPvM to ‘priority hazardous substances’ in WFD and backs EQS and groundwater quality standards for Total PFAS

The European Parliament’s ENVI Committee adopted its [position](#) on the revision of the Water Framework Directive, the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and the

Groundwater Directive on 27 June 2023. The Committee adopted the main proposals from the Rapporteur: introducing an EQS and groundwater quality standard for Total PFAS by 2026 (in addition to the Sum of 24 PFAS proposed by the Commission), introducing extended producer responsibility for producers placing on the EU market products containing priority substances and substances included in the 'watch lists' to cover the costs of water monitoring programmes; removing the maximum number of substances that can be placed on the watch lists proposed by the Commission (5 substances in ground water and 10 in surface water) and reinstating the deadline to phase-out emissions of priority hazardous substances within 20 years of their designation. In addition, the ENVI Committee added PMT/vPvM to the definition of 'Priority hazardous substances' in the Water Framework Directive. It adopted a requirement that threshold values applicable to groundwater should normally be 10-times lower than the corresponding threshold values for surface waters and introduced reduced groundwater quality standard for pharmaceuticals and pesticides. The Committee report also introduced a reduced EQS for atrazine in surface waters and an EQS for Total pharmaceutical active substances. The text will be voted by the European Parliament in plenary session in September.

REACH revision not published before the summer, Commission sticks to announced time frame (Q4 2023)

In a [debate with the European Parliament Environment Committee](#) on 27 June, Kristin Schreiber, director at DG GROW, confirmed that the Commission proposal for the revision of the REACH would not be published before the summer and that the Commission is working to ensure that the proposal is published as announced in the last quarter of 2023.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ deadline to contribute to the [call for evidence](#) on 1,4-dioxane as well as substances and mixtures containing 1,4-dioxane as a constituent or an impurity: **20 July 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to contribute to the [call for evidence](#) and the [open public consultation](#) on the impact assessment to ensure that hazardous chemicals banned or severely restricted in the EU are not produced for export: **31 July 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to reply to the open public consultation for the fitness check of the application of the polluter-pay principle: **4 August 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation: **30 August 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the PFAS restriction: **25 September 2023**

11 Regulatory watch August 2023

European Parliament adds PFAS to the list of pollutants to be reported by operators of industrial installations

The European Parliament adopted its negotiating position on the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive and on the proposal for an Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation in plenary on 11 July 2023. In its negotiating position on the Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation, the European Parliament added PFAS to the list of pollutants which releases in air, water, and soil must be reported above thresholds set in Annex II to the Regulation. The EP also proposed that the Commission reviews Annex II by 31 December 2026 and proposes amendments if necessary.

In its negotiating position on the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive, the Parliament weakened the requirement for national authorities to set the strictest emission limit values possible for installations applying BAT – requirement that the Council had removed in its mandate adopted in April. The EP also added several provisions strengthening the information and consultation of drinking water and wastewater operators: they should be consulted before a permit is granted to an industrial installation discharging wastewater directly or indirectly into surface water (Article 14); they should also have access to monitoring results, when such monitoring is performed in connection with additional measures added to the permit to meet a specific EQS (Article 18). Finally, the EP significantly restricted the conditions for individuals affected by damage caused by IED permit violations to claim compensation. Additional details can be found in the excel sheet. Trialogues for both legislative acts have started in July.

Commission proposal for Toys safety regulation extends generic approach to endocrine disruptors

The Commission published on 28 July its proposal for a Regulation on the safety of toys, repealing the existing Toy Safety Directive (Directive 2009/48/EC). The proposed Regulation extends generic restrictions of substances in toys, which were already existing for CMRs, to endocrine disruptors, substances toxic for a specific organ and respiratory sensitisers. Derogations may be possible following a mandatory safety assessment by ECHA, as well as an assessment of alternatives. The proposed Regulation is the first legislation implementing the commitment of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability to extend the generic approach to harmful chemicals.

No agreement reached between European Parliament and Council on recast F-gas Regulation

Negotiations between the European Parliament and the Council on the recast F-Gas Regulation ended without reaching a deal, as [confirmed by the Parliament rapporteur, Bas Eickhout, on 19 July](#). Negotiating positions from both institutions were diverging significantly, as the European Parliament called for a complete HFC production and consumption phase out in the EU by 2050, while the Council proposed to maintain the phase down schedule of the Commission proposal with some adjustments for the first two periods and the postponing of certain ban dates (e.g. SF6). Negotiations will resume in the fall.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to reply to the [open public consultation](#) for the fitness check of the application of the polluter-pay principle: **4 August 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation: **26 September 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law): **26 September 2023**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Regulation on the safety of toys: **26 September 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the PFAS restriction: **25 September 2023**

12 Regulatory watch September 2023

ECHA to start reviewing substances of concern in batteries in 2024

[Regulation \(EU\) 2023/1542](#) on batteries and waste batteries, adopted in July 2023, entered into force on 17 August 2023. The new regulation requires the Commission, supported by ECHA, to publish a report by the end of 2027 on substances of concern (defined as ‘having an adverse effect on human health or the environment or hampering recycling for safe and high quality secondary raw materials’) present in batteries or used in their manufacture. Based on the findings of this report, the Commission may propose to restrict new substances under the Regulation if ‘an unacceptable risk to human health or the environment [...] that is not adequately controlled and needs to be addressed on a Union-wide basis’ is identified at any stage of the battery’s life cycle. In a [statement](#) published on 17 August, ECHA indicated that they will start working on the report in 2024.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the PFAS restriction: **25 September 2023**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation: **31 October 2023.**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law): **31 October 2023.**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Regulation on the safety of toys: **31 October 2023.**

13 Regulatory watch October 2023

Council and Parliament agree on phase out of F-gases by 2050

On 5 October the Council and the Parliament reached a [provisional agreement](#) on the revision of the F-gas Regulation, which provides for a complete phase out of HFC consumption by 2050. Production rights allocated by the Commission will be gradually phased down from 2024 to 2049. The agreement includes specific phase-out dates for the use of F-gases in certain products, including key sources of PFAS emissions: heat pumps and air conditioning units must use F-gas free alternatives by 2035 and medium and high voltage switchgear by 2030 and 2032. The provision agreement will be submitted to the Council and the Parliament's environment committee for endorsement, before its formal adoption and publication in the Official Journal.

European Parliament supports harmonised classification for groups of substances in its position on the revision of CLP

The Parliament adopted its [position](#) on the revision of the CLP Regulation in plenary on 4 October. Amendments proposed by the Parliament push for more group classification and specify that 'whenever considered scientifically justified and possible by a competent authority or the Commission, proposals for harmonised classification and labelling shall prioritise groups of substances rather than individual substances'. The Parliament also calls on the Commission to assess the introduction of hazard criteria for immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity by 31 December 2025. Other amendments include a ban on environmental claims for chemicals classified as hazardous, an obligation to assess the progress on Non-Animal Methods (NAMs) every three years and a right for citizens to submit evidence of incorrect or missing classification – details included in the [excel sheet](#). As both the Parliament and the Council have adopted their position, negotiations between institutions on the final text can start.

ECHA received more than 5 600 comments on the PFAS restriction proposal

ECHA received more than 5 600 comments from more than 4 400 organisations, companies and individuals to the consultation on the draft PFAS restriction proposal, which closed on 25 September 2023. Almost 60% of comments came from companies and 10% from industry or trade associations; 27% came from individuals and the remaining 4% from other stakeholder groups (see ECHA's [press release](#)). Part of these comments are already available on [the restriction proposal page](#). The comments will be considered by RAC and SEAC in their evaluation of the restriction proposal.

European Parliament adopts its position on water legislation; delays expected on revised lists of surface and groundwater pollutants

The Parliament adopted its position on the revision of the Water Framework Directive (WFD), Groundwater (GWD) and Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) Directives on 12 September 2023 and on the Urban Wastewater Treatment (UWWT) Directive on 5 October. In both cases, the final position of the Parliament largely upheld the reports of the ENVI Committee – details provided in the [excel sheet](#). The Council is expected to adopt its general approach on the UWWT Directive on 16 October. Regarding the other water file (revised lists of pollutants - WFD/GWD/EQSD), progress towards a

Council negotiating position has been slower and a general approach is not expected before next year, according to [ENDS Europe](#).

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Regulation on the safety of toys: **31 October 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law): **3 November 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation: **8 November 2023**.

14 Regulatory watch November 2023

REACH revision likely delayed until next Commission

The European Commission adopted on 17 October 2023 its [work programme for 2024](#), the last one before the EU elections in June 2024. The expected REACH revision is not on the list of new initiatives for the coming year, indicating that the Commission proposal is very likely not going to be published under the present Von der Leyen Commission.

Council backs EPR system in its general approach on the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive

In its [general approach](#) on the revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, adopted on 16 October, the Council backed the Extended Producer Responsibility scheme proposed by the Commission, making pharmaceuticals and cosmetics producers pay for the implementation of quaternary treatment. The Council only amended the Commission text to set a deadline for the application of the EPR system three years after the entry into force of the Directive. The European Parliament, which adopted its position on 5 October, had proposed that the EPR scheme should be complemented with national funding.

Regarding the revision of the list of products subject to the EPR scheme, the Council proposed that the Commission considers the necessity to expand the list in the next evaluation of the Directive (scheduled for 2035 and 2041). The list would then be regularly revised on the basis of the results of the evaluation and new scientific evidence. This is less strict than the Parliament's amendments, which proposed that the Commission reviews the list of products subject to the EPR scheme every five years and is empowered to revise the list by delegated acts. The Council also added in a recital that 'Member States should have the possibility to impose additional requirements to the EPR schemes', without specifying further what are these requirements. On the contrary, the Parliament had clearly introduced the possibility for Member States to add sectors to the EPR scheme based on evidence of the presence of micro-pollutants produced by these sectors in wastewater.

The Council also reduced the obligation to apply quaternary treatment to treatment plants serving populations over 200 000 people (double the threshold proposed by the Commission – 100 000 – and higher than the threshold proposed by the Parliament – 150 000). Other amendments are summarised in the excel sheet.

European Parliament's ENVI committee proposes to ban PFAS in food contact packaging

In its [draft report](#) on the proposal for a Regulation on packaging and packaging waste (replacing the current Directive), adopted on 24 October, the ENVI Committee proposes to ban the placing the market of food contact packaging containing intentionally added PFASs and Bisphenol A, starting 18 months after the date of entry into force of the Regulation (around summer 2025). Possible overlaps with the global PFAS restriction, currently reviewed by ECHA's scientific committees, which does not propose derogations for food contact materials for use in consumer articles, will likely be a point

of discussion with the Council and the Commission. The report from the ENVI Committee will be examined in plenary in November 2023.

European Parliament's ENVI Committee upholds pesticides reduction targets from Farm to Fork Strategy

The [position](#) from the ENVI Committee on the proposed Regulation on the sustainable use of plant protection products, adopted on 24 October, contains binding targets to reduce by 2030 the use and risk of chemical plant protection products by at least 50% and the use of more hazardous products by 65%, compared to the 2013-2017 average, while the Commission had proposed a 50% target for both based on the 2015-2017 average. The Parliament's Agriculture Committee had [proposed](#) to postpone the deadlines to 2035 and to require the Commission to evaluate the feasibility to achieve the Union targets by 2029. The report from the ENVI Committee will be examined in plenary in November 2023.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law): **3 November 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation: **8 November 2023**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback on the European positive lists of substances, compositions and constituents for organic, cementitious, metallic, enamels, ceramic or other inorganic materials, which are authorised for use in the manufacture of materials or products that come into contact with drinking water:
 - [Implementing Decision](#) establishing the positive lists: **16 November**
 - [Delegated Regulation](#) establishing the procedure for amending the positive lists: **13 November**
 - [Implementing Decision](#) establishing methodologies for testing/accepting substances, compositions & constituents in European positive lists: **16 November**
 - [Implementing Decision](#) establishing the procedure and methodologies for testing and accepting final materials: **16 November**
 - [Delegated Regulation](#) establishing the conformity assessment procedure for products that come into contact with drinking water: **16 November**
- ▼ Deadline to contribute to ECHA's [call for evidence](#) on the draft screening report on the presence and risk of Bis(2-methoxyethyl) ether (Diglyme) in articles: **22 November 2023**.

15 Regulatory watch December 2023

Commission publishes the legislative proposal for establishing a common data platform on chemicals

The Commission adopted on 7 December the ‘One substance, one assessment’ legislative Package. The Package includes three legislative proposals deriving from the ‘one substance, one assessment’ initiative, announced in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, aiming to increase the efficiency and coherence of safety assessment of chemicals across legislation. The Package contains a [proposal for a Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals](#) and a [proposal for a Regulation and Directive](#) amending several existing legal acts with the aim of streamlining risk assessment tasks and improving cooperation across EU agencies.

The common data platform will bring all information and data on chemicals from EU agencies and authorities in the same platform. It will include information on physico-chemical properties, hazard properties, use, exposure, risk, occurrence, emissions and manufacturing process of the chemicals, environmental sustainability related information, including climate change related information, on those chemicals, and applicable legal obligations and regulatory process-related information on chemicals. The platform will be composed of seven building blocks, some of which already exist and will be integrated into the platform: 1) the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (‘IPCHEM’); 2) a repository of reference values adopted under EU legislation; 3) a database of study notifications, 4) information on regulatory processes, 5) information on obligations under Union chemicals legislation; 6) a repository of standard formats and controlled vocabularies, 7) a database on environmental sustainability-related data. The common data platform will be created and operated by ECHA, within three years from the entry into force of the Regulation, and will be publicly available.

The Regulation also creates a framework for monitoring chemical risks, measure the effectiveness of chemicals legislation and measure the transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals. This framework includes a set of indicators, to be included in an indicator dashboard on the common platform, an EU early warning system to track emerging chemicals risks, and an observatory for specific chemicals requiring additional scrutiny.

Council and Parliament reach provisional deals on the CLP Regulation, the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) and the Ecodesign Regulation

In December, the Council and the European Parliament reached provisional agreements on three main Green Deal legislative procedures: The revision of the Industrial Emission Directive and the Regulation on the Emissions Portal, the proposed Regulation establishing a framework for setting ecodesign requirements for sustainable products and the revision of the Regulation for the classification, labelling and packaging of chemicals (CLP). Texts of the provisional agreements have not yet been made public – they will be published when the trialogues are finalised. Details to follow in the next regulatory watch.

Pesticide reduction targets rejected in European Parliament

The European Parliament rejected the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Regulation in a plenary vote on 20 November 2023. The text, amended by the ENVI Committee, contained binding targets to reduce by 2030 the use and risk of chemical plant protection products by at least 50% and the use of more hazardous products by 65%, compared to the 2013-2017 average. Following the rejection of the text, a majority of MEPs also voted against a referral back to the ENVI Committee for further deliberations, leading to the closure of the first reading for this file. The ball is now in the Council's Court – if the Council reaches a compromise, it will be sent to the Parliament for a second reading.

The text is on the agenda of the Agrifish Council on 10-11 December to present the presidency's [progress report on the proposal](#). The current compromise still contains the 50% PPP reduction target by 2030 (with 2015-2017 period as a baseline) but leaves each Member States free to decide on its own quantitative objectives, targets, measures and timetables to contribute to the overall EU target. According to the progress report, there is however no clear consensus yet and more time will be needed before the Council general approach can be adopted. In its [programme](#), the Belgian presidency (starting on 1 January 2024) indicated that they will continue the ongoing discussions on the revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticide Directive.

EU Court of Justice rejects final appeal from Chemours to overturn listing of GenX on Candidate List

Chemours' legal challenge following the inclusion of GenX in the Candidate List of substances of very high concern (SVHCs) for authorisation in 2019 had been dismissed by the CJEU in 2022. On 9 November 2023, the Court [dismissed the company's final appeal against the ruling](#), concluding that the grounds of appeal were inadmissible or unfounded.

Final exemption for PFOS under the POPs Regulation to be removed

Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid and its derivatives (PFOS) is listed in Annex I to the POPs regulation, prohibiting or severely restricting the production, placing on the market and use of Persistent Organic Pollutants. The PFOS entry currently includes Unintentional Trace Contaminant (UTC) limits in substances, mixtures and articles and a specific exemption for the use as mist suppressant for non-decorative hard-chromium plating. The [draft Regulation](#) revising the PFOS entry in the POPs Regulation, open for consultation until 1 January 2024, reduces the UTC limits and brings them in line with those for PFOA and removes the exemption.

European Parliament backs the ban on PFAS in food contact packaging

The European Parliament adopted its negotiating position on the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation on 22 November. The final text includes the ENVI Committee's proposal to ban the placing on the market of food packaging containing intentionally added PFAS and Bisphenol A, starting 18 months after the entry into force of the Regulation.

Belgian Presidency programme published – upcoming race to close files before the end of April

Belgium, which takes the presidency of the Council on 1 January 2024, presented its [programme](#) on 8 December. If the presidency committed to finalise two files from the Fit for 55 package, on other Green Deal files – Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive, the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive, and the Air Quality Directive – the presidency indicated that it will ‘advance interinstitutional negotiations’, without committing to finalise the negotiations. The presidency also mentioned its intentions to ‘make every effort to advance negotiations’ on the Soil Monitoring Directive and ‘pursue the sound implementation of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, and foster discussions on some of its aspects, such as microplastics and PFAS’. The Work programme does not mention the revision of the water legislation (WFD, Groundwater and EQS Directives). On health, the presidency indicated it will continue the work on the revised pharmaceutical legislation, without promising the adoption of a Council mandate. Belgium holds the last presidency before the European elections in June 2024 and will have around four months before the Parliament’s session ends to close as many files as possible. Presently, [150 legal files are still under negotiation](#).

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation on data requirements and gradual review of safeners and synergists: **20 December 2023**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft regulation reducing the maximum PFOS concentration allowed as unintentional trace contaminant in substances, mixtures and articles and removing exemptions under the POPs Regulation: **1 January 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals: **5 February 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Regulation on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks and improving cooperation among Union agencies in the area of chemicals: **5 February 2024**
- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Directive on the re-attribution of scientific and technical tasks to the European Chemicals Agency: **5 February 2024**

Transposition of the Drinking water Directive

- ▼ 24 Member States have now transposed the revised Drinking Water Directive (three have not transposed yet (AT, MT, PL) + in BE, transposing acts from the Brussels Capital region are expected early 2024).
- ▼ 15 MS have transposed both PFAS parameters in their law (often with the caveat that it will be decided to use either or both parameters after the publication of the technical guidelines by the Commission); 9 have transposed only sum of 20 PFAS.
- ▼ None of the Member States have adopted stricter parametric values for Sum of 20 PFAS and Total PFAS.
- ▼ Three Member States have extended the parameter Sum of 20 PFAS to additional substances:
 - Denmark has adopted a parameter for Sum of 22 PFAS: the 20 PFAS listed in the DWD + 6:2 FTS and PFOSA

- Italy has adopted a parameter for Sum of 24 PFAS: the 20 PFAS listed in the DWD + GenX, ADONA, 6:2 FTS and C6O4
- Sweden has adopted a parameter for Sum of 21 PFAS: the 20 PFAS listed in the DWD + 6:2 FTS
- ▼ Three Member States have adopted a binding parametric value for the Sum of 4 PFAS (PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFOS), and two have established guideline / recommended values for the Sum of 4 PFAS.

Binding parametric values

Denmark	2 ng/l
Germany	20 ng/l (from 12/01/2028)
Sweden	4 ng/l (from 01/01/2026)

Recommended parametric values

Flanders	4 ng/l (drinking water distributors must strive to meet this target value by March 2028; it is a best-efforts obligation, not an obligation of results)
Netherlands	4.4 ng/l (guideline value from RIVM)

In the wake of the controversy sparked by drinking water contamination with PFAS in Wallonia and Brussels, authorities from both regions have announced supplementary measures for the monitoring of PFAS in drinking water: in Wallonia (which has transposed the DWD and so far stuck to the EU parametric values), the establishment of [alert thresholds of 30ng/l for the Sum of 20 PFAS and 4 ng/l for the Sum of 4 PFAS](#), which will trigger actions from authorities and communication to residents (but are not limit values); in Brussels (which acts transposing the DWD are expected early 2024), a [recommendation not to exceed a threshold of 4ng/l for the Sum of 4 PFAS](#), quite similar to the target value in Flanders, could be established (although likely not yet in the 2024 transposing acts).

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